

Cooking with DAOSPEC

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Abstract

DAOSPEC is a Fortran program written by Peter B. Stetson at the Dominion Astrophysical Observatory (DAO) of the Herzberg Institute of Astrophysics, National Research Council, in Victoria, Canada. DAOSPEC automatically finds absorption lines in stellar spectra, fits the continuum, measures equivalent widths and identifies lines with the help of a laboratory linelist, and also provides a radial velocity estimate. DAOSPEC is designed to work on extracted, one-dimensional spectra that have been binned linearly in wavelength, either in FITS or in IRAF (.imh, .pix) format. This cookbook describes how to obtain, install, configure and use DAOSPEC. This new version includes performance considerations and a list of common problems and solutions based on feedback from the users.

NOTE: Please be always certain to have the latest version of the original program, by contacting Peter B. Stetson at:
<Peter.Stetson@nrc-cnr.gc.ca>.

Additional information can be obtained at:
<http://cadwww.hia.nrc.ca/stetson/daospec>
<http://stars.bo.astro.it/~pancino/projects/daospec.html>

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Chapter 1

Getting Started

1.1 System and Software requirements

DAOSPEC has been successfully installed and tested on: (1) various PCs with Linux RedHat 9.0 or Fedora 1.0 and their fortran g77 compiler; (2) Sun machines running different Solaris versions and their standard f77 fortran compilers; (3) Mac with the Tiger OS and the Intel Fortran compiler.

In order for DAOSPEC to compile properly you need:

- To be able to display the pretty pictures on the monitor, you will need supermongo (<http://www.astro.princeton.edu/~rhl/sm/>) and, in particular, the following libraries: `libplotsub.a`, `libdevices.a` and `libutils.a`¹. Since supermongo is not a free program, you may ask us for a version of DAOSPEC that does not include the graphical interface and therefore does not need the supermongo libraries to compile.
- To work with FITS files, you will need Pence's `cfitsio` library (`libcfitsio.a`) that can be obtained at: <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/software/fitsio/fitsio.html>
- To work with IRAF², you will need the following `IMFORT` libraries: `libimfort.a`, `libsys.a`, `libvops.a`, `libos.a` and `libcompat.a`; they can be obtained at: (<http://iraf.noao.edu>)

¹Please be aware that the supermongo libraries installed through the ESO scisoft compilation of software do not work. You need to compile supermongo from scratch and from the original distribution files in order for DAOSPEC to compile properly. See Section 4.1.2.

²IRAF is distributed by the National Optical Astronomy Observatories, which is operated by the association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under contract with the National Science Foundation.

1.2 Obtaining DAOSPEC

The latest version of the code can be obtained by contacting Peter Stetson (<Peter.Stetson@nrc-cnr.gc.ca>). You will be asked to sign an agreement form and then receive a gzipped tarfile containing the following files:

- `daospec.f` — The source code of DAOSPEC
- `iosubs.f` — Routines for pretty input and output
- `mathsubs.f` — Mathematical routines
- `lnxsubs.f` — Routines specific to Linux machines
- `unxsubs.f` — Routines specific to Unix machines
- `bothsubs.f` — Image I/O routines for FITS and IRAF
- `irasubs.f` — Image I/O routines for IRAF but not FITS
- `fitsubs.f` — Image I/O routines for FITS but not IRAF
- `arrays.inc` — Defines the size of data arrays
- `Makefile.unix` — The makefile to compile DAOSPEC on a Sun
- `Makefile.linux` — The makefile to compile DAOSPEC on Linux
- `daospec.ps` — This cookbook
- `test.fits` — A test spectrum³ to check your installation
- `daospec.opt` — A test configuration file
- `laboratory.dat` — A test laboratory linelist
- `testC.fits` — A sample output continuum file
- `testR.fits` — A sample output residuals file
- `test.daospec` — A sample DAOSPEC results file

³This is a small portion of the Sun spectrum, taken with UVES@VLT with R~100,000. The whole spectrum can be downloaded at:
http://www.eso.org/observing/dfo/quality/UVES/pipeline/solar_spectrum.html

1.3 Installing DAOSPEC

The following makefiles are provided: `Makefile.unix` and `Makefile.linux`. You must first edit the appropriate Makefile, adding the appropriate library paths. If you have FITS images but do not have the IRAF libraries, replace `bothsubs` with `fitsubs` everywhere; if you have IRAF images and do not have the FITS libraries, replace `bothsubs` with `irasubs`. Then rename the makefile and compile DAOSPEC as follows:

```
cp Makefile.<system> Makefile
make daospec
```

DAOSPEC is dimensioned for spectra of up to 1,200,000 pixels (as specified in the parameter `MXSPEC` in `daospec.f`). This will most probably cause a `segmentation fault` error message and crash DAOSPEC if your machine does not have enough resources. You could try to `unlimit` your resources (`ulimit` on Linux) and see if it works. However, we strongly recommend that you change `MXSPEC` in order to match exactly your needs: too high `MXSPEC` values will result in a waste of computer memory. Once you have edited `daospec.f`, you need to recompile the code

```
rm *.o
make daospec
```

1.4 Test your installation

Once DAOSPEC has been successfully installed, you can test your installation by using the test image `test.fits` with its laboratory linelist `laboratory.dat` and its configuration file `daospec.opt` (see next chapter to see more details on running DAOSPEC). First, make sure that the `daospec.opt` file is the appropriate one, otherwise edit it with the following values:

```
or=5
fw=12.5
sh=6031
lo=6689
le=6152.
ri=6172.
re = 0.
mi = -10
ma = 10
ve=3
cr=0
```

```
wa=1
sm=5
re=20
```

Then, make copies of the three sample output files provided:

```
cp testC.fits safe.testC.fits
cp testR.fits safe.testR.fits
cp test.daospec safe.test.daospec
```

Finally, run daospec by simply typing⁴

```
daospec
```

at the `OPT>` prompt type `return`. When asked for an input spectrum, reply `test.fits`. You will see a display appear, showing the progress of continuum fitting and line subtraction procedures (see Figures 2.6, 2.7, 2.8 and 2.9). At the end of the process, three files will be created: `testC.fits`, `testR.fits` and `test.daospec`. If you encounter any problem, please have a look at Chapter 4. If no error message appears and if the three produced files are identical (or very similar) to the ones that were provided in the DAOSPEC package, your installation has been successful, congratulations!

1.5 Problem Reports and Suggestions

A list of common problems and proposed solutions can be found in Chapter 4. If you cannot find the solution to your problem, or if you have any suggestion, please feel free to contact Peter Stetson <Peter.Stetson@nrc-cnrc.gc.ca> or Elena Pancino <elena.pancino@oabo.inaf.it>, but please always remember to provide the exact copy of the program that you are using, along with the fits or IRAF files that produced the problem, and all the related configuration files.

Your feedback will be much appreciated and will help us in producing better documentation and a better version of DAOSPEC. Thanks!

1.6 Release Policy and Acknowledgements

DAOSPEC has been written for a specific purpose, i.e., to measure equivalent width of absorption lines by gaussian fitting on line-crowded spectra. It has been designed to work optimally on high resolution, high signal-to-noise

⁴If your DAOSPEC PATH is not set, you may need to type it in entirely, i.e. `/usr/local/bin/daospec`, or you may want to copy the executable in your working directory and then type `./daospec`.

spectra. DAOSPEC is publicly available for free, in the hope that it can be useful. The author declines any responsibility. Please be sure to use always the latest version of the original code. You are free to modify the code to suit your personal needs, but do it with responsibility and please do not distribute the code (modified or otherwise) to third parties; distributing the code without permission will make the lawyers in Ottawa very angry. If you find any bug or have any suggestion, please contact us.

We are now working on a scientific paper that will describe DAOSPEC in more detail. If you use DAOSPEC to produce and publish any scientific results, please always refer to the paper. For the moment you should simply use the reference “*P. B. Stetson & E. Pancino (2008, submitted to PASP)*”. We would also appreciate if you could add a footnote to DAOSPEC in your paper, containing the following text: “*DAOSPEC has been written by P. B. Stetson for the Dominion Astrophysical Observatory of the Herzberg Institute of Astrophysics, National Research Council, Canada.*”.

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Chapter 2

Using DAOSPEC

DAOSPEC finds and measures the continuum and absorption lines in stellar spectra by iterative gaussian fitting and subtraction procedures. For this reason, DAOSPEC is particularly useful when dealing with spectra that are heavily crowded with absorption lines. A detailed description of how the code works can be found in Steston & Pancino (2008, submitted to PASP). In short, the course of the reduction is as follows:

- Perform a crude initial determination of the continuum level in each pixel.
- Identify lines by searching the valid flux values with a kernel corresponding to the user-specified FWHM.
- From a *preliminary* comparison between the detected lines and the laboratory wavelengths, *estimate* the radial velocity and compute the pixel values of the user-specified wavelength limits (SHORT, LONG, LEFT, and RIGHT).
- BEGIN LOOP...
 - Subtract lines from the original spectrum according to current estimates of centroid positions and line strengths;
 - Redetermine the continuum from the line-subtracted spectrum;
 - Divide the spectrum by the newly determined continuum;
 - Redetermine line centroids and strengths;

PERFORM THIS LOOP FIVE TIMES, cranking up a secret robustness factor each time.

- END LOOP

- Cross-identify lines in the spectrum with lines in the laboratory list; compute mean and standard deviation of implied radial velocities; reject provisional cross-identifications with discrepant implied radial velocities.
- Produce output line list and (if desired) continuum spectrum and subtracted (residuals) spectrum.

The following Sections describe the input files needed, the configuration parameters and the resulting output file(s).

2.1 The Spectra

DAOSPEC works on extracted one-dimensional spectra, that have been rebinned linear in wavelength. They should be FITS or IRAF images (.imh, .pix), containing the standard coordinate system FITS header keywords CRPIX1, CRVAL1 and CDELTA1 (Wells et al. 1981, A&AS, 44, 363; Calabretta & Greisen, 2002, A&A, 395, 1077; Greisen & Calabretta 2002, A&A, 395, 1061; Greisen et al. 2006, A&A, 446, 747) in the spectrum header. These keywords specify the relationship between pixel number and wavelength (usually expressed in Å). *Please note that these keywords comply to the international FITS standard system and therefore they are not instrument specific.*

If your spectra are split in separate echelle order, you can still run DAOSPEC on each of the orders separately, provided that they are all extracted to single, one-dimensional spectra in the formats specified above, and that they contain the standard FITS header keywords specified above.

DAOSPEC is dimensioned to work on spectra with a maximum number of 1,200,000 pixels. This can cause a `segmentation fault` error message and crash DAOSPEC if your machine does not have enough resources. See Section 1.3 to repair this.

2.2 The Linelist

DAOSPEC needs a linelist with laboratory rest wavelengths to identify spectral lines and to estimate the radial velocity. The linelist must be an ascii file, called `laboratory.dat`, and should be in the working directory, together with the spectra.

The first eight characters on each line are the laboratory wavelength of a spectral line. After the first eight characters you can have any text that you want. This will be copied literally into the output file, so you should put here any information that you want fed to some routine that will digest the output from DAOSPEC: species identifications, oscillator strengths, whatever.

You can put any informational header/trailer/embedded lines you want into the file, as long as they do not have anything that looks like a wavelength in the first eight characters. It will be worth your while to make this line list as *complete* and *appropriate* as possible, as it will help the program to find the right radial velocity. Here's a five-line example (with a three-line header):

```
Omega Centauri - Test Star
FORMAT(F7.2,1X,A2,I1,F6.2,I3,F7.2,2a1,3f1.0,F6.1)
lambda  el  kiex  ref  log gf  L01
3643.72 FE1 2.61  2   -1.44  47.2 - blended?
3670.02 FE1 2.85  2   -1.06  56.2
3670.81 CA1 2.48  2   -1.95   0.0 - too weak
3676.31 CA1 2.56  2   -0.99   0.0 - ???
3686.00 TI1 2.94  2   -0.13 113.5
```

Note that although the wavelengths occupy only the first 7 characters of each line, DAOSPEC will nevertheless try to read the first 8 characters as a wavelength. Since in this case the eighth character is a blank, this is acceptable. Any other non-numerical character in column 8 would cause the program to barf. Wavelengths larger than 10,000 Å can have only two decimal places.

2.3 Configuration File and Parameters

DAOSPEC reads the user-specified options (or parameters) from an ascii file called `daospec.opt`, that must be in the working directory together with the `laboratory.dat` and the spectra. If no `daospec.opt` file is provided, all parameters are assigned default values (see below) by DAOSPEC. The same is true for any parameter missing from `daospec.opt`. Numerical values for the parameters are specified by putting:

- at least the first two characters of the parameter label (either upper or lower case);
- an equals sign;
- a numerical value.

Any additional labelling on the line should be separated from the numerical value by at least one blank character. Here is an example of valid `daospec.opt` file:

```
sh=3600
BAD DATA VALUE = 0.
Fwied wice is nice = 12.5
```


Figure 2.1: The three panels show (from top to bottom) how the number of lines identified in `laboratory.dat` varies with the input FWHM, how the total number of lines found varies with FWHM and how the final output FWHM varies with the input FWHM. The correct FWHM=11.3 is marked by a vertical dotted line.

```
le = 4101. Window from H-delta to
ri = 4340 H-gamma
```

Additionally, the options can be modified from the command line of DAOSPEC (see Section 2.4), but these changes are not saved and are lost when exiting DAOSPEC. Here is an example of the parameters:

```
FWHM (px, estimated) = 4.00      ORDER FOR CONTINUUM FIT = 10.00
SHORT WAVELENGTH LIMIT = 3500.00  LONG WAVELENGTH LIMIT = 4518.00
LEFT EDGE OF WINDOW = 3600.00    RIGHT EDGE OF WINDOW = 3700.00
BAD DATA VALUE = 0.00          RESIDUAL CORE FLUX (%) = 1.00
VELOCITY LIMIT (sigmas) = 2.00   WATCH PROGRESS = 0.00
MINIMUM RADIAL VELOCITY = -1.00  MAXIMUM RADIAL VELOCITY = 1.00
SMALLEST EQUIVALENT WIDTH = 15.00 CREATE OUTPUT SPECTRA = 1.00
SCALE FWHM WITH LAMBDA = 0.00    FIX FWHM = 1.00
```

The following sections describe each option in detail. Each section title shows in parenthesis the default value of the option parameter.

Please note that the most crucial parameters for an accurate EW measurement with DAOSPEC are FWHM (Section 2.3.1), ORDER (Section 2.3.2) and RESIDUAL CORE FLUX (Section 2.3.6).

Figure 2.2: A spectrum with a $\text{FWHM} \simeq 5$ pixels is measured with DAOSPEC using a fixed FWHM which is underestimated by 10%, 20% and 30%. As can be seen, this induces differences of EW that can reach high values, and that depend on the EW itself.

2.3.1 FWHM (fw=2.5)

FWHM is your initial estimate of the resolution of the spectrum *in units of pixels*. This is just to get the program started off on the right foot with identifying what is probably a line and what is probably noise. The precise numerical value of this parameter will be adjusted in the course of the reductions on the basis of the actual measured line widths, but the precise list of lines detected in the first place will vary in detail with the value of this parameter (see Fig. 2.1). The correct choice of FWHM will also have an impact on the resulting EW measurements (see below).

Spectral lines are modeled by *saturated gaussian* profiles: that is, they are proportional to

$$G(\lambda) = A e^{(-\delta\lambda^2/2\sigma^2)}$$

transformed through a function

$$F(G) = \frac{G(\lambda)}{1 + G(\lambda)}$$

such that $F(G) \rightarrow G$ as $G \rightarrow 0$ and $F(G) \rightarrow 1$ as $G \rightarrow \infty$. This is adequate for moderately saturated lines, but it cannot of course correctly reproduce seriously saturated lines (i.e., on the square-root/damping part of the curve of growth). The actual FWHM used for the measurements is also influenced by the SCALE and FIX parameters (see below).

Figure 2.3: The two panels show (from top to bottom) how the final output FWHM varies with the ORDER parameter and how the residuals vary with the ORDER parameter.

Choosing the correct FWHM value

As shown in Figure 2.1, wrong input values of the FWHM can lead to slightly wrong output FWHM values (The correct FWHM for Figure 2.1 is 11.3 pixels). To give an idea of the effect that these have on the resulting EW, we used DAOSPEC with a fixed (and wrong) value of the FWHM. As can be seen in Figure 2.2, a wrong FWHM tends to create a trend in the sense that an underestimated FWHM gives underestimated EWs, and the bigger the line, the bigger the mistake.

Therefore, the choice of the input FWHM value is fundamental for an accurate EW measurement. Since DAOSPEC runs relatively fast, we suggest to perform a few tests with different FWHM values on one or two spectra before doing the actual measurements on the whole set. The input FWHM given in `daospec.opt` should differ by less than $\sim 10\%$ and/or a fraction of one pixel from the output FWHM value found by DAOSPEC, which can be found if the first line of header of the output DAOSPEC file (Section 2.5).

2.3.2 Order for Continuum Fit (`or=12`)

ORDER is the order of the Legendre polynomial that will be fit to the continuum level in the spectrum. ORDER = 0 is a constant value, ORDER = 1 is a linear function of wavelength and so on. Anything up to 90th order is permitted by the software. The fitted continuum can be saved in a FITS file if CREATE (Section 2.3.11) is set to 1.

Figure 2.4: A typical FEROS spectrum of a solar type star (kindly provided by A. Bragaglia). Two DAOSPEC Legendre polynomials of different order are overplotted, with an arbitrary vertical offset for clarity.

The special option `ORDER = -1` will disable the continuum fitting, and DAOSPEC will stick its continuum value to 1 (in data numbers). In this case, pre-normalization of the spectra to 1 is strictly required, otherwise the output equivalent widths will be nonsense.

The choice of the continuum order has a very small influence on the resulting *average* EW measurements. If the order is not chosen correctly, there will be regions of the spectrum where EWs are overestimated and regions where they will be underestimated, leading to an increase of the intrinsic spread of the resulting abundances. In particular, if the order is too low and the spectrum has a complicated shape (such as in Figure 2.4), the intrinsic spread of measured EWs can increase a lot (i.e., from ~ 5 mÅ to ~ 30 – 40 mÅ, in the example of Figure 2.4). On the other hand, increasing the order can greatly reduce the residuals (Figure 2.3 and Section 2.3.11), but this decrease can be deceptive, since when employing very high orders, DAOSPEC starts fitting the real features in the spectrum. So the polynomial order should not be set to unnecessarily high values.

Choosing the correct order for continuum fit

As said, `ORDER` has a great impact on the *spread* of the resulting EW measured with DAOSPEC. Therefore we suggest to perform a few experiments with different values of `ORDER` on one or two spectra before performing the final measurement for a complete set of spectra. In particular, setting

CREATE (Section 2.3.11) to 1 and overplotting with IRAF (or similar tools) the continuum spectrum on the original spectrum can help in choosing the correct value. An example of such overplot is Figure 2.4.

To choose the appropriate order for the continuum fit, a good rule of thumb is to compare the scale length of the slope variations in the spectral shape and compare this to the total spectrum length. If the variations are frequent and happen down to a scale length of $1/n^{th}$ of the total length of the spectrum, then the appropriate order to choose is n .

The *effective continuum* computed by DAOSPEC takes into account the background of tiny contaminating features (such as tiny spectral features, spectral defects, residuals of sky lines, etc.) therefore may appear lower than the true continuum, especially in crowded spectra. The users should avoid attempting to artificially forcing the continuum to higher values, because otherwise the EW of contaminated lines will be overestimated. More details and experiments with artificial spectra are presented in the DAOSPEC paper (Stetson & Pancino, 2008, submitted to PASP).

2.3.3 Short/Long Wavelength Limit (sh/lo=1/999999)

SHORT and LONG wavelength limit are the extreme ends of the part of the spectrum that is valid; beyond these wavelengths the data are bad or you just are not interested¹. They should be specified in units of wavelength (typically Å). SHORT and LONG also control the limits of the first display window, if WATCH PROGRESS = 1 (see below and Fig. 2.7).

2.3.4 Left/Right Edge of Window (le/ri=1/999999)

LEFT and RIGHT edge of window permit you to choose a shorter length of spectrum which will be plotted on your monitor (see below and Fig. 2.8), so that you can see in more detail what is happening as the reduction proceeds². They are only effective if WATCH PROGRESS = 1 and they should be specified in units of wavelength (typically Å).

2.3.5 Bad Data Value (ba=0)

The software assumes that the flux values in the spectrum are positive numbers, with absorption lines having smaller numerical values than the continuum. You are informing the software that any pixel values less than the BAD DATA VALUE are defective and should be ignored. If you know that

¹Generally, if you specify SHORT and LONG outside the actual limits of the spectrum, nothing bad happens. With some operative systems and/or fortran compilers, however, the program may crash. If it happens to you, simply choose values of SHORT and LONG that are inside the actual limits of the spectrum you are working on. The same applies to LEFT and RIGHT (Section 2.3.4).

²See footnote on Section 2.3.3 as well.

Figure 2.5: Difference between Equivalent Widths measured with RESIDUAL CORE FLUX = 20% (the appropriate value as measured on the H_{α} line at 6563\AA) and RESIDUAL CORE FLUX = 0%, on `test.fits`.

some stretches of spectrum are unwanted (between echelle orders, humongous broad Balmer lines, telluric features, ...), you can mask them off by using IRAF or other software to set them to numerical values less than BAD DATA VALUE.

2.3.6 Residual Core Flux (re=5)

In real stellar spectra, the center of a line is never really perfectly black because the effective surface of a stellar atmosphere is not at a temperature of absolute zero. By setting RESIDUAL CORE FLUX to some positive value, you are telling the software that the lines should saturate to some particular positive flux value (expressed as a percent of the continuum level).

The RESIDUAL CORE FLUX parameter improves by a few $\text{m}\text{\AA}$ ($\sim 10\%$ of the line strength) the measurements of lines of $100\text{--}200\text{ m}\text{\AA}$, while it has a much larger impact on lines stronger than $200\text{ m}\text{\AA}$ (see Fig. 2.5). If you are interested in strong lines, you may choose to experiment with RESIDUAL CORE FLUX.

Choosing the correct Residual Core Flux value

This is the third of the three parameters that have the stronger impact on EW measurements (the other two being FWHM and ORDER). You can have an idea of the correct RESIDUAL value by looking at particularly strong and saturated lines in your spectrum, such as H_{α} at 6563\AA . For example,

`test.fits` has $RE = 20.0$ (i.e., 20% of the continuum value), while the telluric (i.e., the O_2 band around 6300\AA) and interstellar absorption (i.e., the NaD lines at 5890\AA) features will instead easily go much deeper. For this reason, when DAOSPEC is optimally tweaked to measure weakish stellar features, it will not accurately measure telluric or interstellar features.

2.3.7 Velocity Limit (`ve=3`)

After the reductions are complete, the software will cross-identify lines detected in the spectrum with lines listed in the `laboratory.dat` file, to determine the final stellar radial-velocity estimate and to assign the measured equivalent widths to the matching line IDs. It will determine the radial velocity corresponding to each proposed line identification. Provisional identifications with implied radial velocities more than this number of standard deviations from the mean stellar radial velocity will be regarded as incorrect and the lines discarded (see Fig. 2.9).

2.3.8 Watch Progress (`wa=1`)

`WATCH PROGRESS = 1` means draw pretty pictures on the monitor as the reductions proceed; 0 means do not (recommended for batch processing). We recommend launching DAOSPEC from an `xgterm`, especially if working on Linux.

When you launch DAOSPEC with `WA = 1`, it will first display the DAOSPEC logo (Fig. 2.6), containing the maple leaf of the Canadian flag and the Southern Cross (the symbol of ESO, where part of this work has been carried out). Once you type in the spectrum name, reduction starts. For each of the five big iteration loops, DAOSPEC will first display the whole spectrum along with the residuals of the line subtraction procedure (Fig. 2.7), between the `LONG` and `SHORT` limits. Secondly, it will zoom in a region defined by the `LEFT` and `RIGHT` parameters, where more details can be appreciated (Fig. 2.8). After the five loops are finished and the two plots have been displayed five times, the radial velocity of each identified line is shown versus wavelength (Fig. 2.9). Two lines mark the σ rejection limits specified in `VELOCITY LIMIT`. At this point you can type in the name of the next spectrum to be reduced, or you can just hit the `<ENTER>` key to `EXIT`, and the DAOSPEC logo will appear again.

2.3.9 Min/Max Radial Velocity (`mi/ma=-500/500`)

The star is assumed to have an instantaneous geocentric radial velocity within these limits. Extreme permitted values are -1000 and $+1000$ km/sec (this maximum value can be modified by editing `daospec.f` and changing the value of the `VELLIM` parameter). Specifying a more restricted range of radial velocities through `MIN` and `MAX` will make things go a bit faster

and will reduce the (small) chance that the software will make an incorrect initial guess at the actual radial velocity.

2.3.10 Smallest Equivalent Width (`sm=5`)

The software will not print out results for any spectral line with an equivalent width smaller than this value (expressed in mÅ). It will carry along weaker lines internally, but will not report them in the output file. Since the number of lines in the spectrum is one of the factors that can change the performance of DAOSPEC, setting SM to higher values can make the code slightly faster.

2.3.11 Create Output Spectra (`cr=0`)

CREATE OUTPUT SPECTRA = 1 means produce two output spectra (FITS or IRAF—the same as the input spectrum). The first contains the fitted continuum level as a function of wavelength, on the same wavelength and flux scale as the input spectrum, for overplotting if you want. Its default name is, e.g., `testC.fits` if the original spectrum was called `test.fits`. The second will be the *residual* spectrum, i.e. the original spectrum, normalized to the fitted continuum and with all the lines subtracted. Its default name is, e.g., `testR.fits`. CREATE OUTPUT SPECTRA = 0 means create neither the continuum file nor the residual file.

2.3.12 Scale FWHM with λ (`sc=0`)

When an echelle spectrum is wavelength calibrated and rebinned linear, it will have constant resolution:

$$R = \frac{\lambda}{\delta\lambda} = Const;$$

therefore the line width $\delta\lambda$ will increase with wavelength. If SCALE FWHM = 1, the software will take this fact into account when fitting lines and make FWHM proportional to wavelength. In this case, the whole reduction procedure will be slightly slower and the output FWHM estimate will refer to the center of the spectrum, as specified by SHORT and LONG. If SCALE FWHM = 0, a single FWHM will be used to fit all lines, regardless of their wavelength.

2.3.13 Fix FWHM (`fi=0`)

When FIX = 1, DAOSPEC will not adjust the FWHM during the reduction procedure, but will instead apply the user-provided FWHM value. If SCALE = 1, this value will refer to the center of the spectrum, as specified by SHORT and LONG, and the actual FWHM will be proportional to

Figure 2.6: DAOSPEC initial window.

wavelength (Section 2.3.12). If `FIX` is left to 0, DAOSPEC will automatically find the best FWHM value, based on the residuals of the subtraction procedure.

2.4 Running DAOSPEC

Before running DAOSPEC, we recommend that you put closely related spectra into a common subdirectory, and dissimilar spectra into different directories. Rule of thumb: if two spectra can share a common `laboratory.dat` file³, put them into the same subdirectory. Otherwise, not.

To run DAOSPEC (after you have properly installed it) simply type `daospec` on a terminal (in our experience, it is better to use an `xgterm`, especially with Linux). If DAOSPEC's `PATH` is not properly set, you will have to type it in entirely, i.e. `/usr/local/bin/daospec`, or to copy the program in your working directory and then type `./daospec`.

When launched, DAOSPEC will automatically try to read the `laboratory.dat`⁴ and `daospec.opt` files. Then it will produce this output on screen:

```
FWHM (px, estimated) = 4.00    ORDER FOR CONTINUUM FIT = 10.00
```

³Sometimes it can be useful to separate also spectra that would need different `daospec.opt` files, unless you want to measure them with the same batch process (Section 3.2.2)

⁴If `laboratory.dat` is not present in the directory, DAOSPEC may crash or hang on some systems.

Figure 2.7: The first DAOSPEC display window, showing the continuum normalized spectrum (upper panel) and the line subtracted spectrum (lower panel), within the limits specified by the SHORT and LONG parameters.

```

SHORT WAVELENGTH LIMIT = 3600.00      LONG WAVELENGTH LIMIT = 4518.00
LEFT EDGE OF WINDOW   = 3500.00      RIGHT EDGE OF WINDOW  = 3700.00
BAD DATA VALUE      = 0.00          RESIDUAL CORE FLUX (%) = 1.00
VELOCITY LIMIT (sigmas) = 2.00       WATCH PROGRESS       = 0.00
MINIMUM RADIAL VELOCITY = -1.00     MAXIMUM RADIAL VELOCITY = 1.00
SMALLEST EQUIVALENT WIDTH = 15.00   CREATE OUTPUT SPECTRA = 1.00
SCALE FWHM WITH LAMBDA = 0.00       FIX FWHM             = 1.00

```

OPT>

Now, you can modify the options on the command line, if you like. You simply have to type the first two letters of each option, followed by an equals sign and the numerical value (see also Section 2.3). After you have changed the desired options, or if you like the options as they are, simply type return. However, please note that these changes will not be saved in `daospec.opt`, and will thus be lost when you exit the program. To change the options permanently, you must edit the file `daospec.opt`.

Now DAOSPEC thinks a while and, if `WATCH PROGRESS = 1`, it opens the display window (see Section 2.3.8 and Fig. 2.6) containing the DAOSPEC logo⁵. On the command line, you will be asked for the file name: type it in and hit return. If the filename extension is `.fits`, `.fit`, or `.imh`, you can omit it if you like; if it is anything else, you must include it.

⁵On a few cases, DAOSPEC hung forever at this point, even if it compiled with no error or warning (see Section 4.1.2).

Figure 2.8: The second DAOSPEC display, showing an enlarged region specified by LEFT and RIGHT. The H_{α} line region has been chosen. The continuum normalized spectrum is shown (upper panel), with the identified lines marked. The subtracted spectrum is also shown (bottom panel) with an estimate of the average residual dispersion in the whole spectrum—not just this region. The continuum is determined only from pixels with residual values lying between the two horizontal lines.

(If the filename extension is *anything* other than `.imh`, the image file *must* be in FITS format.) The header keyword `OBJECT` is now displayed, together with the spectrum size in pixels and a first estimate of the radial velocity:

```

                                Input spectrum: WFI512938_U.fits
RED_SCIENCE_REDU

                                Picture size: 27889

                                Estimated radial velocity: +218 km/s

FWHM
4.08

```

The FWHM is continuously updated on the screen, while the display window shows alternately the whole spectrum (Fig. 2.7) and an expanded region specified by the user through the LEFT and RIGHT parameters (Fig. 2.8), until the five big loops are completed. When the procedure ends, the final radial velocity estimate appears along with some basic information, and more details will be shown on the display window (Fig. 2.9).

Figure 2.9: Last DAOSPEC display, showing how the final radial velocity is determined and how discrepant lines are rejected.

```

Final radial velocity: +47.495 km/s
Velocity scatter:      2.168 km/s
Based on:              2701 lines

```

Input spectrum (default EXIT):

Finally, the prompt appears again, asking for a new spectrum name. Typing EXIT (or simply hitting RETURN) at this point exits DAOSPEC.

2.5 Output File

Apart from the continuum and residuals files discussed above, DAOSPEC produces one single ascii file for each spectrum: if the original file was called `test.fits`, the output file will be called `test.daospec`.

Here is an example of DAOSPEC output file:

```

Radial velocity = -0.171   dispersion = 0.429   FWHM = 11.454   158 lines
  matched out of 1070
Relative flux dispersion in residual spectrum = 1.113%
3600.115  3597.494  64.4  20.00  2.088
3600.379  3597.758  82.7  18.86  4.617
3601.731  3599.108  19.0   4.44  0.844
3606.458  3603.832  57.3   7.30  1.587  3603.84  TI1  0.00  1  -3.38  86.9  -blend?
3613.684  3611.053  27.2   5.66  0.839
3613.864  3611.233  19.1   5.59  0.819

```

```

3614.289 3611.657 34.5 9.13 1.586
3635.198 3632.551 34.8 8.02 1.644 3632.56 FE1 2.95 2 -1.03 67.2
(1)      (2)      (3)  (4)  (5)  (6)  (7)

```

The file contains two lines of header (with information about the estimated radial velocity, FWHM, number of spectral lines and residuals) and one line of data for each spectral line found. The columns contain:

- (1) the line center wavelength observed in the spectrum;
- (2) the line center rest wavelength, corrected for the derived radial velocity;
- (3) the measured equivalent width;
- (4) the estimated error in the measurement, derived in the usual way from the least-square fitting procedure;
- (5) a quality parameter, derived from a comparison between the residuals observed in the spectrum in the immediate neighborhood of the line, as compared to the typical residuals in the spectrum as a whole—large values are bad;
- (6) if the line has been identified, this column contains the original laboratory wavelength as it appears in `laboratory.dat`;
- (7) if the line has been identified, the remaining information from `laboratory.dat` is appended literally here.

Chapter 3

Performance Considerations

A typical spectrum of a not too crowded red giant ($R \simeq 45000$, λ 4800–6800 Å, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \simeq -1.3$), with the appropriate configuration parameters, requires a few seconds at most on typical machines (PCs or Mac Workstations). However, being designed for giving accurate results and not for speed, DAOSPEC performs a few loops and iterations and therefore the amount of time required to measure big sets of spectra can become large.

To improve the performance of DAOSPEC, it is necessary to pay attention to a few factors, that are described in detail in the DAOSPEC paper (Stetson & Pancino, 2008 ...). It is also possible to write simple shell scripts that allow DAOSPEC to run in *batch* mode, i.e., to work on several spectra automatically without waiting for the users input after each spectrum has been completed (Section 3.2).

3.1 Factors that Affect Performance

Basically, apart from the computing power of the particular machine used for running DAOSPEC, the most important factors that affect the performance of EW measurements are:

- The MXSPEC parameter (see Section 1.3);
- The FWHM choice (see Section 2.3.1);
- Spectrum length in pixels;
- Number of lines in the spectrum (not in `laboratory.dat!`);

other factors that might have an influence on performance are:

- Optimized compilation;
- Simpler continuum shape and *appropriate* use of a low polynomial order (see Section 2.3.2);

- Using a *fixed* and *not scaled* FWHM, when appropriate (see Sections 2.3.12 and 2.3.13);
- Using a narrow interval of Min/Max radial velocity, if possible (see Section 2.3.9);

3.2 Batch Processing

Like any Fortran program, DAOSPEC can be run from a shell script. This is particularly useful if you have to run it on a number of different spectra with similar characteristics, i.e., sharing the same linelist and most of the DAOSPEC options. Two examples are shown in the following Sections.

3.2.1 A Simple Example

Here is a simple script for reducing multiple spectra (i.e., `star01.fits`, `star02.fits` and so on) with the *same* input parameters (i.e., same `daospec.opt` and `laboratory.dat`) using `csch`, without the `graphics`, and storing screen output in a log file called `logfile`.

```

# !/bin/csh                                # Tell the system where's csh
#                                           # Comment
rm star??.daospec                          # Remove previous output
daospec << DONE >! logfile                 # Run DAOSPEC and save log
FW = 7.5                                    # Set FWHM
WA = 0                                      # Mandatory for batch processing
                                           # Carriage return to exit options

star01                                     # Work on first spectrum
star02                                     # ... second spectrum
star03                                     # ...
star04                                     # ...
star05                                     # ... last spectrum
                                           # Carriage return to exit DAOSPEC
DONE                                       # End of input list for DAOSPEC

```

Please note that empty lines are important, because they are actually carriage returns: you need the first one to exit the options and the second one to exit DAOSPEC. Please also note that removing the `*.daospec` is also very important: if you provide DAOSPEC the name of an *existing file*, it will ask if you want to overwrite it, a question that is not normally asked and that will therefore change the order with which commands are given.

3.2.2 A Less Simple Example

If you still are running DAOSPEC on a list of files, but this time would like to change a few parameters from one spectrum to the next, you can first create an ascii file, containing the rootname of each spectrum in each line, followed by one or more parameters that you may want to change. In this example we will change two parameters, FWHM and SCALE. Here is your ascii file called, i.e., `spectra.lst`:

```
star01 7.6 1.0
star02 9.1 1.0
star03 8.3 1.0
star04 2.5 0.0
star05 5.2 0.0
```

This means that we want to run DAOSPEC with $\text{FWHM} = 7.6$ and $\text{SCALE} = 1$ for `star01.fits` and so on. The following shell script (this time using `ksh`) will read your list, launch DAOSPEC once for each row/spectrum, change the two parameters and save the screen output in a log file for future reference.

```
#!/bin/ksh -f          # Tell the system where's ksh
#                    # Comment
cat spectra.lst | \   # Read your list containing:
while read spec fwhm scale # spectrum name, fwhm and scale
do                      # Start do loop on file's rows
  rm "${spec}".daospec  # Remove previous output
  rm "${spec}"C.fits    # ...
  rm "${spec}"R.fits    # ...
  ./daospec <<END>> "${spec}.log" # Start DAOSPEC and save log
  wa=0                 # Mandatory in batch mode
  cr=1                 # Optional to create fits outputs
  fw=$fwhm            # Feed variable $fwhm to DAOSPEC
  sc=$scale           # Feed variable $scale to DAOSPEC
                      # Carriage return to exit options
  "${spec}.fits       # Feed spectrum name to DAOSPEC
                      # Carriage return to exit DAOSPEC
END                   # End of input list for DAOSPEC
done                 # End of loop, repeat on next row
```

As a result of the above script, you will produce a few files for each of your spectra. For example, `star01.fits` will have now: `star01.daospec`,

the daospec output file with equivalent widths; `star01C.fits`, the fitted continuum; `star01R.fits`, the residual spectrum of the line subtraction procedure and `star01.log`, containing the output that is normally printed on screen.

Chapter 4

Common Problems and Solutions

Since when the first test versions of DAOSPEC were circulated in 2002, several users have sent their feedback and brought to our attention the problems they encountered when installing or running DAOSPEC on many different computers. We summarize here a series of common problems and solutions resulting from these e-mail exchanges.

4.1 Installation Phase

The vast majority of reported problems concerns of course the installation phase, since users have different fortran compilers and system architectures. The most important problems are connected with the supermongo (Section 4.1.2), IRAF (Section 4.1.3) and cfitsio (Section 4.1.4) libraries.

4.1.1 General Problems in Linking Libraries

Problems related with libraries (either supermongo, IRAF, cfitsio or system libraries) can give a variety of different behaviours and error messages. Moreover, the same problem can give different outcomes on different operative systems. We try to list here below the two most typical symptoms of library linking problems. More specific examples of error messages related to particular libraries can be found in the corresponding Sections (from Section 4.1.2 to 4.1.4).

- **Undefined Reference to Symbol**

An error messages appears when compiling, complaining that in some “function” the reference to some “symbol” is undefined. For example:

```

/usr/local/lib/libplotsub.a(point.o)(.text+0x1710): In function 'setsym':
/scisoft/sm/sm2.4.2/src/plotsub/point.c:341: undefined reference
to '__ctype_b'

```

The paths may vary, and you can find some other library name instead of `libplotsub.a`, some other function instead of `setsym` and some other symbol instead of `__ctype_b`. In any case, this kind of error message is always related to a problem with libraries.

• Undefined Reference to <symbol name>

A similar error message appears on some systems, but without telling the name of the library. This makes it a bit harder to identify where the exact problem is, unless you know some of the functions and of the symbols used by each library. For example, all supermongo symbols usually start with something similar to `sm_<something>`. The following error message can be obtained when compiling DAOSPEC:

```

daospec.o(.text+0x7370): In function 'emblem_':
: undefined reference to 'sm_draw_'

```

and it is related to the part of DAOSPEC that draws the canadian leave and in particular to the supermongo `libplotsub.a` library.

• A Checklist of Library Problems and Solutions

Here is a short checklist of things to do if you have library problems in general:

1. check if the library is present on your system;
2. check if the path of the library in your Makefile is correct;
3. if some library is missing, install it (see Section 1.1). Supermongo, IRAF and/or FITS libraries can be optional. See Section 1.1 and the Sections here below;
4. if all the libraries are present and correctly linked, but you still have problems, see the following Sections.

4.1.2 Supermongo Libraries Problems

Supermongo (Hereafter SM) is widely used in astronomy as a plotting tool, and it is available at a modest price. However, the libraries that interface SM with Fortran can give problems that we try to list here below. The names of these libraries are normally: `libplotsub.a`, `libdevices.a` and `libutils.a` (see also Section 1.1).

- **DAOSPEC without SM Graphical Interface**

If you are not able to solve your SM Library problems with the suggestions below, you can always ask P.B. Stetson for a DAOSPEC version without SM libraries and no graphical interface.

- **Error in the SM Library Path**

On most machines and with most compilers, if the library path is wrong, the compiler will report errors similar to the ones in Section 4.1.1, or will complain that the library is not found. However, the following error message came from an alpha workstation where SM was installed properly, but the paths of its libraries were not correctly written in the DAOSPEC Makefile:

```
Fonts file not found
File graphcap is not defined
Can't get graphcap entry for nodevice
No such device nodevice
File graphcap is not defined
Can't get graphcap entry for xterm
No such device xterm
Fonts file not found
I can't read the fonts file so I can't write labels
Maybe you haven't opened a device from non-interactive SM?
```

if this message appears to you, either check the paths of supermongo libraries on your computer or reinstall supermongo from scratch.

- **Typical Hang due to SM Library Problem**

DAOSPEC compiles without problems, but then it hangs forever *before* starting the supermongo graphical display. Sometimes it starts displaying something (a box, some labels) but does not complete the plot and then hangs forever. DAOSPEC has entered an infinite loop. This kind of behaviour completely disappears when setting WATCH PROGRESS=0. This is a typical example of hang due to a problem with supermongo libraries. Most probably, the problem relates to the fact that the SM Libraries are compiled in double precision (see below).

- **SM Libraries Compiled in Double (Float) Precision**

Most often, the SM Libraries compiled in double precision (or float) do not work for DAOSPEC. The precision of the Libraries and of SM itself is decided when SM is compiled and installed on your system. The main problem is due to the fact that double precision SM libraries are generally

called `libplotsub_d.a` instead of `libplotsub.a` and the compiler does not find them, unless you rename the library by removing “_d”, or you change the library paths in the Makefile by adding “_d” to the library names. Most of the times, however, the double precision libraries simply will not work, even if you rename them appropriately. In this case make sure that your computer has the single precision libraries properly compiled somewhere else in the system, and link those instead of the double precision ones.

• Problems with ESO Scisoft SM Libraries

The ESO Scisoft libraries are broken and will not work for DAOSPEC. Recompiling SM is necessary to use DAOSPEC with the graphical interface, otherwise you can ask P.B. Stetson for a SM free version of DAOSPEC.

• Incompatible Symbol Names in the SM Libraries

Sometimes the way SM is compiled in your system causes incompatibility between the SM libraries and the Fortran calls inside DAOSPEC. The symptom is similar to the ones already described in Sections 4.1.1, but the libraries are properly linked and you are sure they contain the symbols that the system is complaining about. This might be due to the different names that Fortran and C compilers give to symbols within libraries. You can verify this by checking the configuration parameters `FORTRAN_APPEND` and `FORTRAN_PREPEND` that can be found inside the SM configuration file called `options.h`. The corresponding section of the file will look like this:

```
/*
 * Different compilers treat C and fortran external symbols differently.
 * For unix systems, the main variants are for fortran externs to have
 * an extra trailing _, and for the fortran and C names to be identical.
 * In the latter case we have to call our fortran-callable versions things
 * like fsm_box; this is achieved by defining these symbols. If neither
 * is defined, we'll define FORTRAN_APPEND as _ .
#define FORTRAN_APPEND _
#define FORTRAN_PREPEND f
*/
```

Within `daospec.f` the SM symbols are called with names of the type `SM_DRAW`, `SM_LIMITS` and so on. For example, if a `PREPEND` “f” is defined within `options.h`, then `daospec.f` should be edited so that all symbols are called `FSM_DRAW`, `FSM_LIMITS` and so on. As another example, if `APPEND` is defined as “_”, then `daospec.f` should be edited so that all symbols are called `SM_DRAW_`, `SM_LIMITS_` and so on.

4.1.3 IRAF Libraries

The IRAF libraries are necessary when you plan to run DAOSPEC on images in the IRAF format (i.e., <image>.imh and <image>.pix files). They are generally called `libimfort.a`, `libsys.a`, `libvops.a`, `libos.a` and `libcompat.a`. They can be obtained at: (<http://iraf.noao.edu>). The problems you can encounter with these libraries are not dissimilar from the ones listed in Section 4.1.1.

• DAOSPEC Without IRAF

If you do not manage to solve your IRAF Library problems with the suggestions of Section 4.1.1, you can always convert all your images into the FITS format. In this case, you need to substitute `bothsubs.o` with `fitsubs.o` in the DAOSPEC Makefile and to recompile DAOSPEC, that will then be able to work only with FITS files and not with IRAF images.

• Problems with `libcompat.a`

This particular library solves compatibility problems of different versions of the IRAF Libraries on some systems. Typically, it is only needed on some Linux systems and some Alpha workstations. More information can be found on the IRAF Website. If you have problems when linking the IRAF libraries you can try removing this library from the library paths in the DAOSPEC Makefile (on some systems apparently it works).

4.1.4 Cfitsio Libraries

To work with FITS files, you will need Pence's `cfitsio` library (`libcfitsio.a`) that can be obtained at: <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/software/fitsio/fitsio.html>. They are very well documented and quite straightforward to install.

• DAOSPEC Without FITS

If you do not manage to solve your `cfitsio` Library problems, you can always convert all your images into the IRAF format (i.e., <image>.imh and <image>.pix files). In this case, you need to substitute `bothsubs.o` with `irasubs.o` in the DAOSPEC Makefile and to recompile DAOSPEC, that will then be able to work only with IRAF images and not with FITS files.

4.2 Running Phase

The following run-time problems and miscellaneous doubts have been pointed out over the last five years by various users.

4.2.1 Hangs

Two conditions are presently known in which DAOSPEC hangs forever, apparently without doing anything.

- **Hang Before Displaying SM Interface**

If DAOSPEC hangs just before displaying the SM graphical interface, of just after plotting a few things (a box, some labels) then most probably there is a problem related to the SM Libraries. Please have a look at Section 4.1.2.

- **Hang Before Even Reading the Options**

Are you sure that the `laboratory.dat` file is in your working directory? Check that the file is there, that the first three lines of the file do not contain any interesting laboratory wavelength (they should be reserved to the header comments), that there are at least 10 valid lines in your list, that the lines really are within the wavelength interval of your spectrum, that there are no empty lines at the end of the file and so on.

Normally, most of the above conditions should not crash or hang DAOSPEC, but we have seen that compiling DAOSPEC on different machines (typically Alpha workstations or some Linux distros) can produce this kind of behaviour.

- **Unexplained hangs**

Could be due to one of the reasons listed in this Section (see above) and in the following Section 4.2.2. Very rarely, library linking or incompatible symbol names (Sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2) can be the cause of a hang.

4.2.2 Errors & Crashes

The following error messages can sometimes appear, and they are all straightforward to correct for experienced computer users.

- **Segmentation Fault**

Typically, a segmentation fault error appears when there are memory problems with the computer. See Sections 1.3 and 3.1 to see how to dimension DAOSPEC or to increase the computer resources.

In less usual cases, DAOSPEC can give a segmentation fault error because there is a problem with the `laboratory.dat` file (see Section 4.2.1) or with the spectrum limits, as described in this Section.

- **Rubbish Characters on the Screen**

When running DAOSPEC with an active SM display (and `WA=1`), the window that should display the DAOSPEC logo (Figure 2.6) and the graphical progress plots opens normally, but then it is flooded with rubbish characters. It is necessary to kill the graphical display window, and the window from which DAOSPEC was launched must be killed as well.

This is due to the fact that you did not launch DAOSPEC from a graphical terminal (`xgterm`). On some machines it is not necessary to specify the `xgterm` command to launch the appropriate window, while on some others it is. To be sure, always launch DAOSPEC from an `xgterm`.

- **Unexplained crash**

Could be due to one of the reasons listed in this Section (see above) and in the previous Section 4.2.1. Very rarely, library linking or incompatible symbol names (Sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2) can be the cause of a crash.

4.2.3 Other Strange Behaviours

Other strange behaviours appear with some machines and with some compilers, but not with others.

- **Asterisks instead of a Radial Velocity**

DAOSPEC does not provide a radial velocity estimate and on the screen a set of asterisks appears instead. If the `laboratory.dat` has some flaw (see also Section 4.2.1), in particular if it has too few good lines (i.e., less than two-three identified lines), DAOSPEC does not have enough information to produce a radial velocity estimate, then the estimate is replaced by asterisks. If the `laboratory.dat` file is totally missing, DAOSPEC will hang forever on some machines, while it will produce asterisks on some other machines. On some machines, DAOSPEC may crash or hang if there are problems with `laboratory.dat`.

- **Requested Wavelength Range not Available**

This error message appears and stops DAOSPEC on some machines (for example some Linux distros) when the spectrum limits (`SHORT` and `LONG` parameters, Section 2.3.3) are set to wavelength values that are external to the actual spectrum limits. Try setting them from 0.1 to 1Å (or whatever

units you use) *inside* the spectrum limits. For example, if your spectrum goes from 5000 to 9000Å, set the limits to 5000.1 and 8999.9Å, or to 5001 and 8999Å.

On most machines, however, DAOSPEC is perfectly able to work on a spectrum that is shorter than the limits set by SHORT and LONG without crashing or complaining. Very rarely, DAOSPEC simply crashes without displaying any error message at all.

4.3 Features (not Bugs)

A few behaviours of DAOSPEC have been reported by alarmed or puzzled users as problems or bugs, but are infact intended features of DAOSPEC or normal things that happen when using computers.

- **The DAOSPEC Continuum is Too Low**

This is due to the fact that DAOSPEC, similarly to DAOPHOT, measures EWs based on an “effective continuum”, which is the hypothetical “true continuum” cleaned of all the unresolved features and spectral defects that would pollute the lines and lead to an artificial overestimate of the EW. This is explained in detail and tested with experiments, in the DAOSPEC paper (Stetson & Pancino, 2008, submitted to PASP). The “effective continuum” is always in good agreement with other codes and methods for clean and non crowded spectra and gets slightly lower than the levels determined by some softwares and some users in the case of crowded spectra.

After discussions with users, and given our own need of testing the continuum placement uncertainty, DAOSPEC has now (since 2008) the possibility of switching off the continuum fitting by setting ORDER=-1 (Section 2.3.2). Using your own continuum determination instead of DAOSPEC’s means that you take responsibility for that (and we do not). If you publish results based on DAOSPEC, but using your own continuum level, please state this very clearly in the paper.

- **The EWs of the Test Spectrum come out Different**

When DAOSPEC is installed and you test your installation as described in Section 1.4, the EW may come out slightly different from the ones originally provided in the DAOSPEC package. If the differences are small you should not worry about that, it is normal when you change compiler and computer to obtain small differences. If they are not small differences, and you did not change the `daospec.opt` and `laboratory.dat` files, nor the `test*.fits` files then please contact us.

- **My Spectrum is not in Å, DAOSPEC does not Work**

It might sound silly, but DAOSPEC can work with spectra in whatever units *as long as those units are the same as in the laboratory.dat file*. Also, your EWs will not be in mÅ anymore. Sorry for pointing that out, but a few users fell into that sort of trap, so we think that it is maybe worth reminding that.

Thats all, Folks!